

**Computing
Cultural Heritage**
Fall 2021

Designed by
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Contents

- 3** Introduction
Ben Lee
- 9** Reflections
Seminar Students
- 13** Cultural Heritage and Social
Media
Meena Muralikumar
- 19** Thoughts on Collectionscope
Sam Solomon

Introduction

Ben Lee

This zine represents the culmination of CSE 590T/LIS 598A: Computing Cultural Heritage, a graduate seminar at the University of Washington. From large-scale systems for searching the web to the datasets that machine learning practitioners utilize to train their models, our collective cultural heritage is in many ways the substrate of computer science. Indeed, cultural heritage practitioners including humanists, librarians, and archivists have been influential in shaping the discourse surrounding the socio-technical implications of computing. In this seminar, we explored various topics within computer science through the lens of cultural heritage: data visualization, human-AI interaction, search & recommendation, crowdsourcing, web archiving, design & UX, classification, best practices, and education. The pedagogical goals of this course were two-fold: first, to survey these topics in computer science, and second, to explore how they manifest within the context of cultural heritage. We covered one

topic every week, with the first meeting devoted to the CS-oriented literature for the topic, and the second meeting devoted to the sociotechnical implications of the topic in practice. During these second meetings, we spoke with cultural heritage practitioners at institutions across the country to learn about the roles of computing in their work, research, and stewardship.

In designing this seminar, a primary goal of mine was to bring together students from across the University of Washington. I was thrilled that 23 students enrolled, from programs as far-ranging as Computer Science & Engineering, Electrical Engineering, Mechanical Engineering, Human Centered Design and Engineering, Asian Languages and Literature, Cinema and Media Studies, Communication, Information Management, and Library & Information Science. The very idea of computing cultural heritage evades disciplinary boundaries, and the discussions that emerged from this course were proof of this. The range of perspectives offered throughout the quarter proved to be incredibly fruitful and generative, shaping the discussions into formative and memorable learning experiences that I find myself continu-

ing to return to on a daily basis.

In this zine, you will find students' reflections and contributions that draw from this Autumn Quarter's worth of discussions. The "Reflections" section consists of concise takeaways offered by many students in the course. The "Contributions" section contains essays written by a few students who expanded on topics that had particularly interested them. I invite you to read the zine and explore the course syllabus if you would like to learn more.

Before I conclude, I would like to thank a host of people who have made Computing Cultural Heritage possible. First and foremost, I am so grateful for the students who made the course into a learning experience not only for each other but also for me. I thank the student contributors of the zine for volunteering to add material on their own time during a pandemic. In particular, I would like to thank Lucille Njoo for her incredible work designing this zine. In UW CSE, I thank Dan Grossman, Elise deGoede Dorough, and Dan Weld for their encouragement and help in making this course possible. Lastly, I would like to thank the guest

speakers who graciously offered their time, wisdom, and advice throughout the quarter:

- Michael Haley Goldman (Executive Director, New Hampshire Humanities)
- Jaime Mears (Senior Innovation Specialist, LC Labs, Library of Congress)
- Meghan Ferriter (Senior Innovation Specialist, LC Labs, Library of Congress)
- Jim Casey (Assistant Professor of African American Studies, History, and English, The Pennsylvania State University)
- Trevor Owens (Director of Digital Content Management, Library of Congress)
- Brian Foo (Data Visualization Artist, American Museum of Natural History)

- Joshua Ortiz Baco (Ph.D. Candidate in Spanish & Portuguese, University of Texas at Austin)
- Thomas Padilla (Senior Director of Collections, Technology, and Partnerships, Center for Research Libraries)
- Eileen Jakeway (Innovation Specialist, LC Labs, Library of Congress)
- Sarah Salter (Assistant Professor of English, Texas A&M Corpus-Christi)

I am incredibly thankful to have been a part of Computing Cultural Heritage, along with so many wonderful students, colleagues, scholars, practitioners, and leaders.

Sincerely,
Ben Lee
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COMPUTING CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Reflections

This class really opened up this area at the intersection of computing and cultural heritage for me. A recurring theme across all topics was thinking about how advances in computing can benefit cultural heritage but also deliberating about how we can learn from library sciences to inform computing research and practice (ex: ethical practices in AI/ML, considering the complicated problems of classification etc). — *Meena Muralikumar*

One of the biggest challenges for a lot of really important collaboration across disciplines is figuring out who out there knows what-- just another reminder to keep reading widely, not just in your particular area! That'll give you the best chance of figuring out who you need to be talking to. (This is as much a reminder to myself as anything haha!) — *Sofia Serrano*

Classifying data into categories is incredibly difficult and says a lot about the societal context in which the categories were made. — *Madeleine Grunde-Mclaughlin*

I have learned that sometimes data visualization can not give us the correct information. It might misguide us at some point, so we need to pay attention to the underlying meaning/culture heritage/other factors of the data visualization. In short: Sometimes, the data visualization can not fully reflect the issue behind the view, such as historical issues, cultural heritage, etc. (I never thought in this way before I had this class, and I really appreciate Ben for making this amazing class for us!). — *Yuanfeng Li*

The way this class brought together different disciplines to explore computing and cultural heritage was incredibly eye opening. The topics we explored are constant reminders to always remember the importance of cultural and social dynamics in how we explore and interpret data, even as we apply new technologies and computing tools to this old challenge. — *Shengzhi Wang*

In my last quarter as an information management student, I felt it was a good opportunity to study the history of computers (and it's various fields such as UX and Data Science), how they came to be, and how they are being applied in today's world. Having a teacher who was well read in the topic, and who invited experts to speak was a good opportunity to hear diverse opinions, and my favorite session was on machine learning and search. — *Zoshua Colah*

Even though I come from the library field, I was not aware of all the ways the Library of Congress is exploring machine learning, and it was fascinating to read about all the projects they have going and talk with them about how they are starting to think about their collections as data. For me, this class was a great window into the things computer scientists are thinking about, and I found lots of connections that I intend to continue researching in the future. — *Stephanie Leary*

It's easy to look at computing as a cool nifty novelty, and it is cool and nifty — but beneath it there are layers and layers of social dynamics, cultural heritage, and history that both affect and are affected by the computing tools we make. — *Lucille Njoo*

Coming from the Master of Communication course, after a computer science major in undergrad, this course brought together so many interdisciplinary concepts of design, AI, humanities, visualization, together and the readings that were assigned on different topics felt complementary to each other to form a complete rounded picture, so really kudos to Prof. Ben for such a tremendous curriculum, and one of the other great things about him was how he frequently encouraged the class to share links of studies in that area and how he was curious to expand his knowledge. The class was interactive and the additional references shared in the classes were highly useful.

Some of my favourite topics were about search user interfaces, clustering and categorization and how different technical databases sought different search results which was so eye-opening. — *Niharika Arora*

In my first quarter as a library and information science student, I'm so glad I took this class because it brought a computer science perspective to overarching ideas I was learning about in other classes. The readings and discussions helped me think about the ways in which librarians and data/computer scientists can work together to build better systems. — *Sam Solomon*

COMPUTING CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Cultural Heritage and Social Media

Meena Muralikumar

We surveyed a range of topics within computer science and discussed how it manifests within the cultural heritage. To extend this list, this contribution is meant to understand if and how social media interacts with cultural heritage and affords its exploration.

My first encounter with Instagram accounts that represent digital cultural archives was through 1) [pari.network](#) (86.8k followers) and 2) [brown-history](#) (596k followers). I discovered them through Instagram, possibly around the same time, and the recommendation algorithm could have played a role as well. PARI - People's Archive of Rural India - acts as both an archive and living journal to capture the snapshots of rural life in India. Their official website itself compares how museum and library visits have fallen in India, but the Internet only gains visitors and users. Hence, PARI asserts that the

web is the right place to build and host a combination of audio, video, photo and text archives. Some of the principles that underlie this effort are: 1) all content is licensed under the Creative Commons, 2) the stories and narratives are owned by the rural people and their communities, and 3) access is free and anyone can contribute as long as it meets the mandate of the archive (so it is subject to some editorial control). Its intentional effort to be on the web and create awareness and educate people with these stories has probably led to its Instagram presence as well. It's an intriguing idea that it serves both as a living journal and an archive. Today's social media account might fit the bill of journalism. How long before it serves as an archive?

In contrast, @brownhistory is not an official source. It is a podcast and a store that accepts donations and is run single-handedly. The Instagram account is an extension, but what is fascinating about this account is how it serves as a digitized archive. Followers can submit their stories and pictures from their personal history, which get posted on @brownhistory. It often brings to light stories that don't or cannot get

featured in a formal sense. It also contextualizes details around immigration, colonization, and racism that might not always feature in mainstream or formal archives. It is almost a crowd-sourced collection of personal archives that together constitute a rich, compelling account of ‘brown history’.

Notably, the US National Archives also has an official Instagram account - @usnatarchives along with several others such as Smithsonian and New York Public Library(<https://www.archives.gov/social-media/instagram>, <https://www.instagram.com/smithsonianarchives/?hl=en>, <https://www.instagram.com/nypl/>).

What does it mean for archives to be available this way, on social media? Why do people follow them and how does it influence the people who follow these accounts? What are some of the thorny issues associated with such practice? An online survey revealed that most archival services believed that a social media presence provided them greater visibility and direct interaction with users [2]. Jensen analyzes how archives and museums use Instagram for digital sharing, outreach and commu-

nication and hence, engage in what seems like a participatory culture. However, while social media applications offer a space for interaction, Jensen notes how institutions set the scene. The concluding question is quite evocative - “what kind of role should and could the user have in the appraisal process?” [3].

Social media can also function as sites of archival materials. For example, social media has been instrumental in organizing and effecting grassroots and activist movements. Now, both the Occupy Wall St movement and Ferguson Unrest have their own archives. The Library of Congress also has plans in place to archive their tweets from 2006 as social media gains prominence in disseminating information to the public [1] though this collection and archival process is now limited to certain themes and current events [4].

References

1. https://www.loc.gov/static/managed-content/uploads/sites/6/2017/02/twitter_report_2013jan.pdf
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4. https://blogs.loc.gov/loc/files/2017/12/2017dec_twitter_white-paper.pdf

Thoughts on Collectionscope

Sam Solomon

Brian Foo's Collectionscope (left) presents museum materials in a more engaging way than if the items were simple entries on a webpage. Now they have mass and dimension, displayed like objects that take up space. It is a very fitting way to showcase a museum's collection.

But it also reminds me of this one viral photo I saw years ago showing what it would look like

if everyone alive on the planet right now were piled up in the Grand Canyon (right). People found this image disturbing, maybe because of the ant-like mountain of supposed “people” laying on top of each other.

It's an important reminder that when using visualization of any type of data, but especially when that data comprises humans or culture heritage, it's important to apply context and understanding. Otherwise, a data visualization can look absurd, or even downright grotesque.

*Grand Canyon photo from:
https://www.huffpost.com/entry/humans-fit-in-to-grand-canyon_n_5255076*

